

Supplementation of Neem and Nishyinda Leaves as Growth Promoters in Quail

Md. Shahriar Haque, Rakibul Islam, Fahima Binthe Aziz, Md. Mahmudul Hasan & Mst. Misrat Masuma Parvez

Abstract:

The aim of this work was to investigate the effects of Nishyinda (*Vitex nigundo*) and Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves on growth performance and hematologic parameter in quail. A total of 40, 14th day old Japanese quail were randomly assigned into groups T0, T1, T2, and T3 and continued up to 42 days of age. Birds were reared on cage. The group T0 was kept as a control whereas group T1, T2 and T3 were fed 2% Neem, 2% Nishyinda and 2% (1%Neem +1% Nishyinda) respectively, with commercial diet. At 14 days of age the initial average live body weights of T0, T1, T2 and T3 were 25.33 ± 0.88 , 26.67 ± 0.88 , 25.67 ± 0.33 , 26.33 ± 0.88 respectively. On the 42 days of age the final live weight of T0, T1, T2 and T3 were 117.33 ± 0.88 , 124.33 ± 1.76 , 121.33 ± 1.20 , 130.67 ± 1.45 respectively. The highest body weight was obtained in T3 followed by T0 which differ significantly ($P < 0.01$) from each other. Feed conversion ratio (FCR) for the T3 and T1 were from the control group which improved significantly were 4.17 ± 0.09 and 4.38 ± 0.05 respectively during 2 to 6 weeks of age. But no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference among the mean value of hematologic parameters of quails. It is concluded that supplementation with 2% of combined (1%) Neem and (1%) Nishyinda leaves powder in diet in treatment groups caused significant increase in live body weight and weekly weight gain, feed consumption and FCR as compared to that of control group of quail.

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INTRODUCTION

Various herbal products are being used as growth promoters in the poultry rations like Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and Nishyinda (*Vitex negundo*). Neem tree as one of the most researched tree in the world has attracted world-wide prominence due to its vast range of medicinal properties like antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antiprotozoal, hepatoprotective and various other properties without showing any adverse effects Kale *et al.*, (2003). Nishyinda (*Vitex negundo* L.) is a hardy plant, flourishing mainly in the Indian subcontinent (Molla *et al.*). It possesses phyto-chemical secondary metabolites, which impart a variety of medicinal uses. The leaves of Nishyinda may be applied locally to swellings from rheumatoid arthritis and sprains (Sultana *et al.*). The juice of the leaves is used for the treatment of foetid discharges. The principal constituents of the leaf juice are casticin, isoorientin, chrysophenol D, luteolin, p-hydroxybenzoic acid and D-fructose (kamal *et al.*). Herbal agents could serve as safer alternatives as growth promoters due to lower cost, reduced toxicity and minimum health hazards (Nath *et al.*). Biological trials of certain herbal formulations as growth promoter have shown encouraging results and some of the reports have demonstrated improved weight gain and feed efficiency, lowered mortality, and increased immunity and viability in poultry (Kumar, 1991). Some herbal growth promoters exert therapeutic effects against liver damage due to feed contaminants like aflatoxin (Ghosh, 1992). Polyherbal products promote growth and feed efficiency of birds because of their antibacterial and hepatoprotective properties (Wankar, 2009). Due to adverse side effects arising from the use of synthetic forms of growth promoters, consideration should be given to alternative natural supplements. Neem and Nishyinda leaves (*Azadirachta indica*, and *Vitex negundo*) have been found to be rich source of active ingredients essential to the growth of farm animals. Also, they are relatively abundant. This study hereby investigates the combined effect of Neem and Nishyinda leaves supplementation on the growth performance and hematological parameter of quail. Therefore, the present study was designed to see the effects of Neem and Nishyinda on growth performance with following objective: To know live body weight, feed conversion ratio and the effects of Neem and Nishyinda leaves supplement on hematological parameter of quail.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted the poultry research unit under the department o Physiology and Pharmacology, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science & Technology University, Dinajpur. The duration of experiment was 28 days (From 10 February, 2018 to 09 March, 2018).

Management of experimental Quails

Neem and Nishyinda leaves were collected from the research field of HSTU. 40 quails of 2 weeks old were randomly selected and equally divided into 4 groups (T₀, T₁, T₂ and T₃). Quails of Group 'T₀' 10 quails were kept and are considered as control, fed only with commercial quail ration. The Neem and Nishyinda leaves were dried and grinded. The grinded leaves were added with commercial layer ration and served to different groups of quail. Quails of Group 'T₁' 10 quails were supplemented with formulation of 20 gm grinded Neem leaves per kg feed. Chickens of Group 'T₂' 10quails were supplemented with formulation of 20 gm grinded Nishyinda leave per kg feed. Quails of Group 'T₃' 10quails were supplemented with formulation of 10 gm grinded Neem leaves plus 10 gm grinded Nishyinda leaves per kg feed. All the 40quails of control and treated groups were closely observed for 4 weeks to complete the research work following steps were followed as,

Measurement of parameters

Feed intake, Body weight gain, growth and Hematological Test (Total Erythrocyte Count, Hemoglobin concentration, Packed cell volume, Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate) of quail.

Hematological Test

Blood samples were collected from wing vein of layers of both control and treated groups to study the effect of experiment at blood serum level. The blood parameters were observed as follows;

Determination of Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC)

Total erythrocyte count was done following the method described by Lamberg and Rothstein (1977). Well-mixed blood sample was drawn with red blood cell diluting pipette exactly up to 0.5 marks of the pipette. Outside of the tip of the pipette was wiped with cotton. Then the

pipette was immediately filled with the red cell diluting fluid (Hayem's solution) up to 101 marks. The free end of the pipette was wrapped around with the rubber tube stretching to both the ends and held with thumb and middle finger. The content of the pipette was mixed thoroughly by shaking with 8-knot motion for 3-5 minutes. Then the counting chamber was placed with special cover glass under microscope using low power (10 x) objectives. After discarding 2 or 3 drops of fluid from the pipette, a small drop was placed to the edge of the cover glass on the counting chamber as the entire area under the cover glass was filled by the fluid. One-minute time was spared to allow the cells to settle on the chamber under the cover glass. Taking 5 larger squares (4 in the 4 corners and the central one) of the central large square, the cells were counted from all the 80 small squares (16 x 5) under high power objectives (45 x). After completion of counting, the total number of RBC was calculated as number of cells counted x 10, 000 and the result was expressed in million/ μ l of blood.

Determination of Hemoglobin Concentrations (Hb)

The N/10 hydrochloric acid (HCl) was taken in a graduated tube up to 2 marks with the help of a dropper. Well-homogenized blood sample was then drawn into the Sahli pipette up to 20 cm. mark. The tip of the pipette was wiped with sterile cotton and the blood of the pipette was immediately transferred into the graduated tube containing hydrochloric acid. This blood and acid were thoroughly mixed by stirring with a glass stirrer. There was a formation of acid hematin mixture in the tube by hemolysing red blood cells by the action of HCl. The tube containing acid hematin mixture was kept standing in the comparator for 5 minutes. After that distilled water was added drop by drop. The solution was mixed well with a glass stirrer until the color of the mixture resembled to the standard color of the comparator. The result was read in daylight by observing the height of the liquid in the tube considering the lower meniscus of the liquid column. The result was then expressed in g %. The above procedure was matched by the Hellige hemometer method as described by Lamberg and Rothstein (1977).

Determination of Packed Cell Volume (PCV)

The citrated well mixed blood sample was drawn into special loading pipette (Wintrobe pipette). The hematocrit or PCV was recorded by reading the graduation mark; the percent volume occupied by the hematocrit was calculated by using the following formula as described by Lamberg and Rothstein (1977).

$$\text{PCV}\% = \frac{\text{Height of the red cell volume in cm}}{\text{Height of total blood in cm}} \times 100$$

Determination of Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR)

The fresh anticoagulant blood was taken into the Wintrobe hematocrit tube by using special loading pipette exactly up to 0 marks. Excess blood above the mark was wiped away by sterile cotton. The filled tube was placed vertically undisturbed on the wooden rack for one hour. After one hour the ESR was recorded from the top of the pipette. The result was expressed in mm/in 1st hour.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigated the effect of Neem and Nishyinda leaves extract supplementation on feed conversion and growth performance of quail. The results of these studies are discussed under following headings;

Live body weight gain

Table 01. Effects of Neem and Nishyinda on live body weight gain at 7 days interval

Days	Control (group T ₀) n=10	Treatment (Group T ₁) n=10	Treatment (Group T ₂) n=10	Treatment (Group T ₃) n=10	p value	Level of significance
Day 14 mean±SEM (gm)	25.33±0.88	26.67±0.88	25.67±0.33	26.33±0.88	0.629	NS
Day 21 mean±SEM (gm)	45.33±1.20	46.67±0.88	45.67±0.33	47.33±1.44	0.548	NS
Day 28 mean±SEM (gm)	64.67±1.45 ^a	70.33±.88 ^{bc}	67.67±0.67 ^{ab}	72.33±0.88 ^c	0.004	**
Day 35 mean±SEM (gm)	89.67±1.45 ^a	94.67±1.76 ^a	91.00±1.53 ^a	102.33±1.45 ^b	0.002	**
Day 42 mean±SEM (gm)	117.33±0.88 ^a	124.33±1.76 ^b	121.33±1.20 ^{ab}	130.67±1.45 ^c	0.001	**
Weight gain (gm)	92.00±1.53 ^a	97.67±1.20 ^{ab}	92.33±2.91 ^a	104.33±2.19 ^b	0.009	**

** = Significant at 1% level of significance (P<0.01) * means significant at 5% level of significance (P<0.05) NS = Not significance (P>0.05)

Table 1. Live body weight was recorded first day of examination. Then every week live body weight was recorded up to 42 days of experiment. Table 1 revealed that quails of Group T₃ (supplemented with 2% Neem and Nishyinda) got the maximum weight (p<0.01) followed by Group T₁ (supplemented with 2% Neem) and group T₂ (supplemented with 2% Nishyinda) among all of the experimental groups and the control group T₀ (without supplementation of Neem or Nishyinda) got the lowest body weight. This may be attributed to the beneficial effects of Combine supply of Neem and Nishyinda. Supplementation of Neem, Nishyinda and Papaya leaf in poultry feed improved the weight gain of the quail in this study. These results are in line with the findings of Meraj (1998), who reported that higher weight gain in broilers, drinking water and feed supplemented with Neem, Nishyinda and Papaya. The improvement in body weight, feed efficiency is similar to the finding of Kamal *et al.*, (2015), who observed

significant ($P < 0.01$) improvement in live weight of broiler chicks than control diet when they were fed with combined 2% Neem and Nishayinda replacing same meal, while lower live weights were recorded in control group.

Recording of Feed Intake

Table 02. Effects of Neem and Nishayinda supplement on weight gain, feed consumption, feed conversion ratio

Variable	Treatment	Average weight (Mean±SEM) (gm)	P value	Significance level
Initial live weight (gm) on 14 day	T ₀	25.33±0.88	0.629	NS
	T ₁	26.67±0.88		
	T ₂	25.67±0.33		
	T ₃	26.33±0.88		
Final live weight (gm) on 42 day	T ₀	117.33±0.88	0.001	**
	T ₁	124.33±1.76		
	T ₂	121.33±1.20		
	T ₃	130.67±1.45		
Weight gain (gm)	T ₀	92.00±1.53 ^a	0.009	**
	T ₁	97.67±1.20 ^{ab}		
	T ₂	92.33±2.91 ^a		
	T ₃	104.33±2.19 ^b		
Feed consumption (gm)	T ₀	430		
	T ₁	428		
	T ₂	425		
	T ₃	435		
FCR	T ₀	4.68±0.76 ^b	0.024	*
	T ₁	4.38±0.05 ^{ab}		
	T ₂	4.61±0.15 ^b		
	T ₃	4.17±0.09 ^a		

** = Significant at 1% level of significance ($P < 0.01$) * means significant at 5% level of significance ($P < 0.05$), NS = Not significance ($P > 0.05$)

Feed conversion ratio

Table 2 revealed that quails of Group T₃ (supplemented with 2% Neem and Nishyinda) got the maximum weight ($p < 0.05$) followed by Group T₁ (supplemented with 2% Neem) and group T₂ (supplemented with 2% Nishyinda) among all of the experimental groups and the control group T₀ (without supplementation of Neem or Nishyinda) got the lowest body weight. Kamal *et al.* (2015) reported chickens fed diets containing 2% Neem and Nishyinda powder significantly improved feed conversion ratio compared to control group.

Determination Of Hematological parameter:

Table 03. Effects of Neem and Nishyinda leaves powder on Hematological Parameters of quail.

Blood Parameters	Day	Treatment group				Significance value
		T ₀ (Mean±SEM)	T ₁ (Mean±SEM)	T ₂ (Mean±SEM)	T ₃ (Mean±SEM)	
TEC	21 Day	2.03±0.33	2.13±0.33	2.07±0.33	2.20±0.58	NS
	42 Day	2.13±0.00	2.30±0.00	2.17±0.00	2.27±0.00	NS
Hb	21 Day	8.23±0.33	8.50±0.12	8.30±0.12	8.50±0.06	NS
	42 Day	8.43±0.67	8.67±0.67	8.40±0.06	8.70±0.12	NS
PCV	21 Day	36.20±0.12	36.40±0.12	36.30±0.12	36.50±0.12	NS
	42 Day	36.30±0.12	36.56±0.12	36.38±0.10	36.73±0.07	NS
ESR	21 Day	10.30±0.06	10.20±0.06	10.25±0.03	10.10±0.06	NS
	42 Day	10.06±0.06	10.20±0.12	10.00±0.06	10.13±0.12	NS

** = Significant at 1% level of significance ($P < 0.01$) * means significant at 5% level of significance ($P < 0.05$), NS = Not significance ($P > 0.05$)

Total Erythrocyte Count (million/ mm³)

Total erythrocyte count is presented in (Table 3). The values of TEC in all treated groups and control group were more or less similar and the values were within the normal range. These values show a little fluctuation they were not statistically significant ($p>0.05$).

Estimation of Hemoglobin (gm/dl)

Hemoglobin content is presented in (Table 3). The values of Hb in all treated groups and control group were more or less similar and the values were within the normal range. These values show a little fluctuation they were not statistically significant ($p>0.05$).

Packed Cell Volume (%)

Packed cell volume is presented in (Table 3). The values of PCV in all treated groups and control group were more or less similar and the values were within the normal range. These values show a little fluctuation they were not statistically significant ($p>0.05$).

Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (mm/ in 1st hr)

Erythrocyte sedimentation rate content is presented in (Table 3). The values of ESR in all treated groups and control group were more or less similar and the values were within the normal range. The highest ESR was recorded in Group D and lowest in Group A. Although these values show a little fluctuation they were not statistically significant ($p>0.05$).

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that supplementation with combined 2% of (1% Neem and 1% Nishyinda) leaves powder in diet in treatment group (T₃) caused significantly ($P<0.01$) increase in the body weight compared to control group (T₀). Feed conversion ratio (FCR) improved significantly for T₃ and T₁ which were 4.17 ± 0.09 and 4.38 ± 0.05 respectively during 2-6 weeks of age. FCR for T₂ and T₀ were poorer i.e. 4.61 ± 0.15 , 4.68 ± 0.76 . But the no significant ($P>0.05$) difference among the mean value of hematologic parameters of quails.

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